
Excess capacity of solar collectors Alpisbayev.A.P.

Alpisbayev Amanlik Polatbayevich Student of the Faculty of Construction of the KMU named after Berdak.

Annotation: The article discusses the necessity of solar collectors and useful design solutions. Gilt words: glitter, collector, glitter, microclimate, glass container.

All the countries of the world that use renewable energy sources (RES) are relevant: countries that import fossil fuels - energy resources to reduce energy poverty; countries that use their own fossil fuel reserves - to improve the ecological situation; countries that use fossil fuels - to improve the socio-economic conditions of the population.

The largest solar collector heat extinguishers are connected to the solar collector due to heat radiation and convection due to open insulation. These can be up to 90% of the total heat loss of solar collectors, which is why the selection of open insulation for the heat sink is a crucial step in the design of solar collectors.

Solar collectors are distributed equally reflectively. Reflectors (concentrators) solar collectors are used when the temperature of the waste water exceeds the temperature of the concentrated solar radiation due to the reduced heat reception potential compared to the flat solar collector.

In the case of solar collectors, single glasses are used in an open insulation retina with a mean temperature of reception of 100°C and an ambient temperature of -20°C and a thermal conductivity of $0.13\text{ m}^2\text{ K} / \text{W}$. $20\text{ Watt} / (\text{m}^2\text{-K})$ in the same conditions with a selective (low emission) coefficient of heat transfer to the center of a single layer equal to 0.36 m^2 ; $0,38\text{ m-K} / \text{Watt}$. Open insulation may be more or less soluble than the types of open insulation described above, which use vacuum-circulating packets in the open insulation retinue, so that the heat permeability of the solar collectors is less than that of the vacuum without convection.

Excess capacity of solar collectors.

Firstly, the need for a solar collector can be realized by changing its non-electrical component.. This makes it possible for the sun's rays to be absorbed into the collector field at a temperature of 90° , which in turn makes it possible for the solar apparatus to be absorbed into the collector field.

The efficiency of the solar collector is the probability that the useful heat will reach the collector field

$$\eta_k = \frac{Q}{I} = \frac{L_{c\rho}(t_{ж2} - t_{ж1})}{I}$$

Ways to exceed the capacity of collectors:

- Improve the thermal insulation of collectors;
- Increase the thickness of the layer;
- Lower the temperature of the outside of the collector;
- Vacuum surrounding space;
- Concentration of energy;
- Configure a multi-stage collector ignition scheme

Exposure to solar collectors is measured, and thermal absorption types of solar radiation are measured...

The most widespread forms of open solar insulation are single-pane polycarbonate plates without selective (bottom-up) layering, and deep layered capillary structures. The maximum thermal resistance coefficient that can be eroded in this type of open insulation environment is 0,38 m² K / W - the thermal conductivity coefficient of the nested polycarbonate. Vacuum-coated coatings, depending on the degree of vacuum and the number of selective layers, of polycarbonate with a thickness equal to or greater than 1 mm. Selective coatings are applied to the glass surfaces that absorb thermal infrared radiation (wavelength of more than 3 microns , maximum 10 microns) from the thermal receptive therapy of the solar collector. This is equal to the magnitude of (0,38). 0,78 microns) are almost transparent ..

Vacuum glass packets with a spacing of ~ 0.1 - 0.2 mm. This vacuum is pumped under a pressure of 10⁻³ - 10⁻⁴ mm Hg, as a result of which the heat loss due to the lack of heat conductivity of the rare gases in the vacuum chamber is significantly reduced. Therefore, the heat loss of the vSP is significantly increased, so that the vacuum between the sources is maintained in the case of glass-ceramic glazing with a diameter of 0.25 - 0.4 mm and a height of 0.1 - 0.2 mm. Vacuum glass packages not more than 25-40 mm.

It is recommended to use vacuum glass packets from solar collectors for thermal insulation of energy-saving (solar) buildings. The thermal resistance of selective layered vacuum glass packets is 0.77 m²μK / W and the permeability is 0.80 N. As a result of the use of vacuum glass packets , heat-retardants and room heating requirements are reduced.

The thermal insulation of vacuum glass packages has a number of advantages over the use of polycarbonate in the smooth capillary structure of analogues, due to the fact that the thickness of the insulation is not sufficiently high (not more than 0,6); In addition, the service interest of vacuum glass packages exceeds the service interest of polycarbonate.

Currently, Uzbekistan has a lot of opportunities to develop renewable energy, as well

as to market solar collectors.. The author believes that in order to meet the requirements for solar collectors, the price of solar installations should be evaluated in the interest of the consumer, and that the solar collector should be evaluated for the possibility of replacement and replacement in the summer. In addition, solar collectors can be installed in buildings, such as. architectural element (for example , a flat façade element with a roof) that facilitates the transfer of building materials to the dam. Finally, the price of solar collectors should be lowered and action should be taken to exceed their needs.

It has been demonstrated that it is possible to exceed the efficiency of solar collectors in vacuum glass packaging environments, which significantly reduces heat loss to the environment.

Used literature.

1. [Electronic resource]. This is a list of the cities and towns in Siberia:. This is the first time in the history of our country that we have been able to do this.
2. [Electronic resource]. the technosphere. It is also necessary to increase the efficiency of solar collectors and vacuum packs ..